

Investigating the Effectiveness of Construction Practices in Delayed Residential Projects in Gadhinglaj City through Time and Cost Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Construction schedule delays could also be explained by means of the late completion of construction add comparison of designed schedule of project. If the explanations of the development projects schedule delay are found then the project schedule delay in construction may be reduced. During this study, factors of schedule delay were selected after the past review of literature then arranged them in primary sets. On following the survey outcomes, the highest causative groups and factors (that require more consideration) of delays in kokan region were explained.

KEYWORDS: Delay, overcast, overtime, etc

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INTRODUCTION

Now a days, construction activity is the second largest activity in the world. This construction activity provides largest economy to the country and helps in development of the country and provides important role in urbanization, development of economy and standard of living of peoples. Delay is the greater problem to the construction activity. Delay also create impact on the quality, time, cost and safety of the construction project. Delay can be expressed as the time elapsed on the expected time of a schedule time of project. It is the time elongation process in which time required to complete an activity is more than that prepared while scheduling.

Objectives of the Research

The aim of research is at investigating the effectiveness of construction practices. To attain the aims, Objectives are identified as follows:

1. To review the explanations for delaying the development projects.
2. to seek out the notice and limitations of the effectiveness of current construction practices.
3. To analyse the effectiveness of construction practices employed in current projects through time and value perspective and to spot the practices which don't seem to be adopted effectively.

4. To analyses this construction practices through time and value perspective.
5. to seek out out the possible solution to enhance the development practices.

SCOPE OF RESEARCH

The project scope is to research the effectiveness of construction practices in delayed residential projects and finding the effective solutions regarding on the issues to attenuate time and price perspective of construction projects. it's supported minimization of the time and price overrun of the long run construction of residential projects by implementing effective solutions on limitations of the development projects. The residential construction projects are growing rapidly because of the event of town. Hence it's necessary to the adoption of the effective solution of the development practices

JUSTIFICATION FOR THE RESEARCH

The literature study identified that various issues and effects of the time overrun in the construction projects and these studies are based on questionnaire survey and interview technique to find out most contributing factors that cause a delay in the projects. Above literature studies showing the rank importance of those factors by analytical means with

the help of relative importance index method and showing the need for general precautions have to be taken to minimize delay in construction projects. Awareness about the effective use of construction practices can help to minimize the time overrun in the construction practices.

LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

After the recognition, many works of research had certain limitations. For that research, there is small investigation relating to residential construction projects in Gadhinglaj city areas and mainly focused on the only residential construction projects in Gadhinglaj city areas and which are belonging as certain cost range of those projects. Data collected from respective site is taken as confidentially and data of the construction projects collected from respective sites only.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Initially, review of literature is made to know the factors and groups of delays in construction projects and this factors are classified according to their groups and questionnaire survey format is made. This questionnaire survey format is carried forward to receive feedback from experts in construction projects like contractors, owners and consultants, etc.

DATA COLLECTION

In that, data of the questionnaires survey format from the various construction projects are received and interview techniques is also used to find out the certain reasons of delay. In data collection, format of questionnaires survey are sent to delayed residential construction projects in the gadhinglaj city areas and feedback from the respective construction project is received.

DETAILS ABOUT THE SELECTED CONSTRUCTION PROJECT

After the systematic sampling study of section A of questionnaire survey, according to specific interval study of site manager in type of respondent, 5 to 10 numbers in year experience of respondent and cost between 1 to 15 crore cost of construction project, five construction projects was selected to analyze the construction practices through its lack of effectiveness.

TYPES OF DELAYS:

1. Critical or noncritical
2. Excusable or non-excusable
3. Excusable delay with compensation
4. Excusable delay without compensation
5. Non-excusable delay
6. Compensable or non-compensable
7. Concurrent or non-concurrent

REASONS FOR DELAY IN THE CONSTRUCTION PROJECT IN MANJULA HEIGHT PROJECT

1. Absence of knowledge of consultant in construction.
2. Complications between design engineer and consultant.
3. Late in performing inspection and testing.
4. Late in revising and approving design papers.
5. Lack of skill of contractor
6. Unsuitable construction procedures
7. Ineffective planning and scheduling
8. Rework due to errors
9. Complication in design
10. Design errors made via designers
11. Errors and late in producing design papers
12. Wrong understanding of owner's necessities by designer

RECOMMENDATION

Many construction projects in Gadhinglaj city are often running into troubles and time completion failures. So, it may result in an increase in time and cost overrun of that project. That studies show that what are the critical factors of causing a delay in construction projects. Many a Previous case studies had been shown the various factors and methods to minimize delays in construction projects but still these projects are going delay in their time and cost due to various reasons.

It indicates that there is either lack of awareness of the suggested construction practices or there are limitations for the effective adoption of their suggestion

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this study, factors are collected from the literature survey and based on these factors questionnaire form is prepared and got an opinion from the construction site in the manjula apartment the construction project.

The top most factor for causes delay in construction project is lack of materials, lack of Modern Equipment's, lack of resources and lack of use of appropriate construction methods and lowest one is lack of communications.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Shebob, N. Dawood, R. K. Shah, Q. Xu. (2012). "Comparative Study of Delay Factors in Libyan and the UK Construction Industry", Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management, 19:6, pp.688-712.
- [2] TowhidPourroostam and Amiruddin Ismail (2012), "Causes and Effects of Delay in Iranian Construction Projects," International Journal of Engineering and Technology vol. 4, no. 5, pp.598-601.
- [3] Ibrahim Mahamid and Nabil Dmaid (2013). "Risks Leading to Cost Overrun in Building Construction from Consultants Perspective". The organization, technology, and management in construction"; An International Journal 5:2 pp.860-873.